

Classimetry of Polygonal Chains (CMPC)

(English edition)

Chapter 1. The Alphabet of Directions

V.L. Khaikov

"Not Just Triangles" Research Initiative

Krasnodar, Russia

khvadim121@gmail.com

ORCID: 0000-0003-1433-3562

Individual chapter under construction

Version: Ch-1(ver-1)

Date: May 25, 2026

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20376728

© V.L. Khaikov, 2026. CC BY 4.0

Part I

Unity of discrete and continuous descriptions of polygonal chains

1 The Alphabet of Directions

1.1 Eight Directions: Axial and Sectoral

1.1.1 The Space of Directions

Let a Cartesian coordinate system (x, y) be fixed in the plane \mathbb{R}^2 . Denote by

$$\mathbb{V} = \mathbb{R}^2 \setminus \{(0, 0)\}$$

the set of non-zero vectors. In order to encode the edges of polylines and subsequently to associate R -functions with them, we need a discrete description of direction that satisfies:

- (i) each symbol of the path code corresponds to a whole equivalence class of vectors;
- (ii) the mapping $\mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ is surjective;
- (iii) the boundaries between classes coincide with the coordinate axes (where the classical R -function loses its sign-discriminating ability).

[!] R -functions (Rvachev functions) were first proposed by Vladimir Logvinovich Rvachev (1926–2005), a Soviet and Ukrainian applied mathematician and engineering scientist.

A note on notation: In this edition, the sign [!] is used to mark author's remarks that are not part of the main mathematical exposition but provide important context.

1.1.2 Definition of the Alphabet of Directions

Definition 1.1 (Alphabet of directions). The alphabet of directions is the set

$$\mathcal{A} = \{ \rightarrow, \nearrow, \uparrow, \nwarrow, \leftarrow, \swarrow, \downarrow, \searrow \},$$

consisting of eight symbols that characterize directions of motion in the plane. Each symbol is interpreted as an equivalence class of vectors from \mathbb{V} with respect to the following relation:

$$\mathbf{v} \sim \mathbf{w} \iff \operatorname{sgn}(v_x) = \operatorname{sgn}(w_x) \text{ and } \operatorname{sgn}(v_y) = \operatorname{sgn}(w_y),$$

where $\operatorname{sgn}(0)$ is undefined, and vectors with a zero component form separate classes (axial directions).

Remark 1.1. The alphabet \mathcal{A} contains:

- (i) **4 axial directions** (one coordinate is zero, the sign of the other is fixed);
- (ii) **4 sectoral directions** (both coordinates are non-zero, their signs are fixed).

1.1.3 Axial Directions

Definition 1.2 (Axial direction). An **axial direction** is a direction corresponding to vectors collinear with one of the coordinate axes of the Cartesian system. In terms of signs:

$$\begin{aligned} (\rightarrow) &\equiv \{(a, 0) \mid a > 0\}, & (\leftarrow) &\equiv \{(a, 0) \mid a < 0\}, \\ (\uparrow) &\equiv \{(0, b) \mid b > 0\}, & (\downarrow) &\equiv \{(0, b) \mid b < 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

Properties of axial directions:

- (i) For any vector with an axial direction, one coordinate is identically zero.
- (ii) Axial directions are **closed sets** in the topology of \mathbb{V} (they contain limit points from the sectoral side).
- (iii) The classical R -function \wedge^0 does not work for axial directions — this is the **ray problem** (discussed in detail in Chapter 3). Regularized \tilde{R} -functions are introduced to handle them.

[!] In the Russian edition, regularized R -functions were denoted by R' . However, during discussions, in order to avoid any confusion with the notation for a derivative, it was proposed to replace the prime with a tilde. Hence the symbol \tilde{R} used throughout this English edition.

1.1.4 Sectoral Directions

Definition 1.3 (Sectoral direction). A **sectoral direction** is a direction corresponding to vectors whose both coordinates are non-zero and have fixed signs. Formally:

$$\begin{aligned} (\nearrow) &\equiv \{(a, b) \mid a > 0, b > 0\}, & (\nwarrow) &\equiv \{(a, b) \mid a < 0, b > 0\}, \\ (\swarrow) &\equiv \{(a, b) \mid a < 0, b < 0\}, & (\searrow) &\equiv \{(a, b) \mid a > 0, b < 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

Properties of sectoral directions:

- (i) Each sectoral direction is an **open set** in \mathbb{V} (its boundaries — the coordinate axes — are excluded).
- (ii) The mapping $\mathbb{V} \rightarrow \{\nearrow, \nwarrow, \swarrow, \searrow\}$ is surjective onto vectors with non-zero coordinates.
- (iii) For each sectoral direction there exists a classical R -function built on \wedge^0 (see Table 1.1).

Remark 1.2 (Relation to polar angle). In polar coordinates (r, θ) , $r > 0$, sectoral directions correspond to open intervals of length $\pi/2$:

$$\begin{aligned} \nearrow &\leftrightarrow (0, \pi/2), & \nwarrow &\leftrightarrow (\pi/2, \pi), \\ \swarrow &\leftrightarrow (\pi, 3\pi/2), & \searrow &\leftrightarrow (3\pi/2, 2\pi). \end{aligned}$$

Here (a, b) denotes an open interval; **no concrete angle value** (e.g., $\pi/4$) belongs to the definition — it serves merely as an illustration of membership.

1.1.5 Elementary R/\tilde{R} -Functions: Hierarchy and Self-Similarity

Definition 1.4 (Elementary direction function). Let $d \in \mathcal{A}$ be a direction from the anisotropic alphabet. An **elementary direction function** associated with d is an analytic expression $F_d(x, y)$ satisfying:

- (i) For any vector $\mathbf{v} = (x, y) \in \mathbb{V}$ belonging to the class d , we have $F_d(x, y) > 0$.
- (ii) For $\mathbf{v} \notin d$ the value $F_d(x, y)$ may be zero or negative, but the sign of F_d does not necessarily coincide with membership in d ; this property appears only at the level of conjunction of edges (Chapter 2).
- (iii) F_d is constructed by a uniform template for all directions of the same type (sectoral — via \wedge^0 , axial — via regularization).

Hierarchy. Elementary functions constitute the atomic level (in the sense that they cannot be further subdivided into sub-functions) of constructing the R -function of a complex polyline:

$$R_{\text{total}} = F_{d_1} \wedge^0 F_{d_2} \wedge^0 \dots \wedge^0 F_{d_n}.$$

No other operations (such as \vee^0) are required at this level — conjunction provides the intersection of half-planes corresponding to each edge. The hierarchy manifests itself as:

- (i) *Atoms* — elementary functions (a single edge as an expression of one direction);
- (ii) *Molecules* — two or more edges (a single edge corresponds to an "atom", not a "molecule"; the conjunction of at least two elementary functions yields a "molecular" structure);
- (iii) *Equivalence classes* — the set of all "molecules" characterized by the same path code.

[!] In the list above, the words "atoms", "molecules", and "molecular" are used as analogies (allegories) to aid intuition. They are not formal terms of classimetry; the formal hierarchy is defined solely by the conjunction operation.

Self-similarity. If a polyline consists of a single edge with direction d , its R -function coincides with the elementary function F_d . If the same direction d appears in a longer polyline, F_d enters the conjunction unchanged. This allows us to:

- (i) recursively construct R -functions for polylines of any length;
- (ii) extract common sub-blocks in different path codes;
- (iii) compute derivatives with respect to parameters without rebuilding the entire function (Chapter 7).

The R vs. \tilde{R} distinction. Not all elementary functions F_d are R -functions in the sense of the classical R_0 system. Classical R -functions are defined only for sectoral directions, where both coordinates are non-zero. For axial directions, the classical definition leads to a loss of sign-discriminating ability (the *ray problem*, Chapter 3). Therefore we introduce regularized \tilde{R} -functions, which:

- (i) approximate the behavior of the classical R -function as $\delta \rightarrow 0$;
- (ii) preserve positivity inside the class d ;
- (iii) provide the smoothness necessary for differential analysis.

Thus, in Table 1.1, the symbols R and \tilde{R} denote not merely "type of function" but belonging to different branches of construction: classical (after V.L. Rvachev) and regularized (extended). Both, however, satisfy the definition of an elementary direction function and support the hierarchical, self-similar structure of classimetry of polygonal chains.

1.1.6 Table of Elementary R/\tilde{R} -Functions

Table 1.1

Elementary R/\tilde{R} -functions of directions

Symbol	Direction	Condition on the vector	Type of function
\rightarrow	Axial	$a > 0, b = 0$	\tilde{R}
\leftarrow	Axial	$a < 0, b = 0$	\tilde{R}
\uparrow	Axial	$a = 0, b > 0$	\tilde{R}
\downarrow	Axial	$a = 0, b < 0$	\tilde{R}
\nearrow	Sectoral	$a > 0, b > 0$	R
\nwarrow	Sectoral	$a < 0, b > 0$	R
\swarrow	Sectoral	$a < 0, b < 0$	R
\searrow	Sectoral	$a > 0, b < 0$	R

Remark 1.3. Concrete analytic expressions for R and \tilde{R} will be given in Chapters 2 and 3 respectively. At this stage, the important point is the separation itself and the understanding that each direction is associated with its own elementary function.

1.1.7 Relations between Directions

Definition 1.5 (Oppositeness). The direction $\bar{d} \in \mathcal{A}$ is called **opposite** to $d \in \mathcal{A}$ if for any vector $\mathbf{v} \in d$ the vector $-\mathbf{v}$ belongs to \bar{d} :

$$\overline{(\rightarrow)} = (\leftarrow), \quad \overline{(\nearrow)} = (\swarrow), \quad \overline{(\uparrow)} = (\downarrow), \quad \overline{(\nwarrow)} = (\searrow).$$

Remark 1.4. Unlike oppositeness, orthogonality is not defined on the class of directions, since for any two distinct sectoral directions one can find both orthogonal and non-orthogonal pairs of vectors. Orthogonality makes sense only for concrete representative vectors, not for equivalence classes.

1.1.8 On the Completeness of the Alphabet of Directions

Lemma 1.1 (Minimality). The alphabet \mathcal{A} is minimal for satisfying the following conditions:

- (i) Surjective mapping $\mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$;
- (ii) For each sectoral direction, the elementary function has the form $\pm x \wedge^0 \pm y$ with fixed signs;
- (iii) Axial directions are separated into their own classes because the classical R -function is inapplicable to them in principle.

Sketch of the proof. Increasing the number of directions (say, to 16) would violate minimality but would not add new R -functions, since any narrowing of the angular interval inside $(0, \pi/2)$ is still described by the same function $x \wedge^0 y$. Decreasing the number of directions (e.g., merging (\nearrow) and (\rightarrow)) is impossible because their elementary functions are different and cannot be reduced to one another. □

2 Path Code as an Implementation of the Route Idea

2.0.1 From a Single Edge to a Route

In §1.1 each edge (vector) of a polyline was assigned a symbol from the anisotropic alphabet \mathcal{A} — its direction in the plane. In order to describe the whole polyline consisting of n successive edges, we must fix the order in which the vertices are traversed.

Definition 2.1 (Path code). Let γ be a polygonal chain with n edges given by a sequence of vectors $\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_n$, where $\mathbf{v}_k \in \mathbb{V}$. The **path code** (P -code or simply code) of γ is the tuple

$$P\text{-code}(\gamma) = (d_1, d_2, \dots, d_n) \in \mathcal{A}^n,$$

where $d_k \in \mathcal{A}$ is the direction of the edge \mathbf{v}_k in the sense of Definition 1.1.2.

Remark 2.1. Because the mapping $\mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ is surjective, each path code corresponds to an infinite set of geometrically different polylines that differ in edge lengths and concrete angles inside the open intervals.

[!] The Russian term for "path" is «ПУТЬ». Both words consist of four letters, one syllable, and carry a similar range of meanings: route, trajectory, direction, even destiny (in Russian). The author considers this coincidence — not a translation choice but a natural correspondence — a fortunate sign for the central concept of classimetry.

2.0.2 Finiteness of Codes for Fixed Length

Lemma 2.1 (Finiteness of the number of codes). For a fixed number of edges n there exist exactly $|\mathcal{A}|^n = 8^n$ distinct path codes (as formal tuples of length n).

Proof. Each of the n edges independently takes one of the $|\mathcal{A}| = 8$ directions. By the Cartesian product rule we obtain 8^n combinations. \square

Remark 2.2. As will be shown in Chapters 4–5, not all of these path codes are geometrically realizable when closure or non-self-intersection conditions are imposed. Moreover, different codes may describe polylines that are equivalent up to continuous deformation (see §1.3 and Part II).

2.0.3 Path Code as a Discrete Invariant

The path code has the property of **discrete stability**: under small changes of the vertex coordinates that transform the vectors \mathbf{v}_k without moving them outside the boundaries of their respective equivalence classes, the path code remains unchanged.

Definition 2.2 (Cell of a code). The set of all polylines having a fixed path code (d_1, \dots, d_n) is called a **cell** in the parameter space (for example, \mathbb{R}^{2n} for n vectors). The cell is open and connected.

A change of the path code occurs only when the boundary is crossed, i.e., when at least one of the vectors \mathbf{v}_k lands on a coordinate axis, which causes a sign change of one of its coordinates or makes it zero. Transitions of this kind are analyzed in Chapter 6.

2.0.4 From Path Code to R -Function

According to the hierarchy principle (§1.1, item 5), the R -function of a whole polyline is built as the R -conjunction of the elementary R - and \tilde{R} -functions of its edges:

$$R_{\text{total}}(x_1, y_1, \dots, x_n, y_n) = F_{d_1}(\mathbf{v}_1) \wedge^0 F_{d_2}(\mathbf{v}_2) \wedge^0 \dots \wedge^0 F_{d_n}(\mathbf{v}_n),$$

where F_{d_k} is the elementary function of direction d_k (R for sectoral, \tilde{R} for axial, see Table 1.1).

Remark 2.3 (Modularity). By analogy with large panels in construction, any continuous segment of a polyline with a fixed path code constitutes a structural unit. It is associated with its own R -function (conjunction of elementary F_d). A complex polyline is assembled as a composition of such units (possibly nested), where the R -function of the whole polyline is the conjunction of the R -functions of its fragments.

2.0.5 Computing Path Codes

Example 2.1 (Two-segment polyline with sectoral edge directions). Let $\mathbf{v}_1 = (2, 1)$, which according to Table 1 corresponds to the direction symbol (\nearrow), and $\mathbf{v}_2 = (1, -3)$ — direction (\searrow). Then

$$P\text{-code} = (\nearrow, \searrow).$$

Using the classical R -function (full expression in Chapter 4):

$$R(x_1, y_1, x_2, y_2) = (x_1 \wedge^0 y_1) \wedge^0 (x_2 \wedge^0 (-y_2)).$$

Example 2.2 (One-segment polyline with an axial edge direction). Let $\mathbf{v}_1 = (5, 0)$ (direction symbol (\rightarrow)). Then

$$P\text{-code} = (\rightarrow).$$

The \tilde{R} -function (with regularization parameter $\delta > 0$):

$$\tilde{R}(x_1, y_1) = \frac{x_1 \cdot \delta^2}{y_1^2 + \delta^2}.$$

Here it is important that $y_1 = 0$, and the function takes the value $x_1 > 0$, which is correct for a ray.

2.0.6 Relations between Path Codes

Definition 2.3 (Sign reversal of a code). For a path code (d_1, \dots, d_n) define its **opposite code** as $(\bar{d}_1, \dots, \bar{d}_n)$, where \bar{d}_k is the opposite direction (Definition 1.1.8). The opposite code corresponds to a polyline rotated by 180° .

Definition 2.4 (Cyclic shift). For closed polylines (Chapter 5), path codes differing by a cyclic shift are regarded as **equivalent**, since they describe the same contour with a different choice of the starting vertex.

Definition 2.5 (Reverse code). The code obtained by reversing the order of the edges and replacing each direction by its opposite corresponds to traversing the same polyline in the opposite direction.

Remark 2.4. The equivalence relations on path codes (cyclic shift, reversal, sign reversal) will be used in Part II to reduce the 8^n formal codes to a smaller number of geometrically distinct classes.

3 Equivalence Classes of One-Segment Polylines in the Plane

3.0.1 Problem Statement

Let a one-segment polyline be a vector $\mathbf{v} = (x, y) \in \mathbb{V}$. By Definition 1.2.1, its path code consists of a single symbol $d \in \mathcal{A}$ corresponding to the direction of this vector.

However, different vectors can yield the same path code. Moreover, from the standpoint of classimetry it is important *not* to distinguish vectors that can be transformed into each other by a continuous deformation that does not change the structure of the R -function and does not cross the boundaries of classes (the coordinate axes).

Definition 3.1 (Equivalence of one-segment polylines). Two non-zero vectors $\mathbf{v}, \mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{V}$ are called **equivalent** if:

- (i) $\text{sgn}(v_x) = \text{sgn}(w_x)$ and $\text{sgn}(v_y) = \text{sgn}(w_y)$;
- (ii) there exists a continuous curve $\mathbf{v}(t) \in \mathbb{V}$, $t \in [0, 1]$, such that $\mathbf{v}(0) = \mathbf{v}$, $\mathbf{v}(1) = \mathbf{w}$, and for no t does any coordinate of $\mathbf{v}(t)$ become zero.

Remark 3.1. Condition (i) is equivalent to \mathbf{v} and \mathbf{w} belonging to the same direction class $d \in \mathcal{A}$ (see Definition 1.1). Condition (ii) excludes crossing the coordinate axes.

3.0.2 Classification

From Definition 1.1 we directly obtain the following lemma.

Lemma 3.1 (Number of equivalence classes). The set \mathbb{V} of all non-zero vectors is partitioned into exactly $|\mathcal{A}| = 8$ equivalence classes of one-segment polylines. Each class is in one-to-one correspondence with a symbol $d \in \mathcal{A}$.

Proof. The mapping $\mathbf{v} \mapsto (\text{sgn}(v_x), \text{sgn}(v_y))$ gives a partition into $3 \times 3 = 9$ sign combinations, including $(0, 0)$. But $(0, 0)$ is excluded because $\mathbf{v} \neq (0, 0)$. The remaining 8 combinations are:

- (i) four with one zero sign — axial directions;
- (ii) four with non-zero signs — sectoral directions.

Each combination forms a connected open set in \mathbb{V} , which is what we had to prove. \square

3.0.3 Representative Vectors for Directions

Although the classes are defined as sets (sectoral classes are open, axial classes are one-dimensional rays), for practical calculations it is often convenient to choose so-called *representative vectors* lying strictly inside the corresponding intervals. The method for constructing them may vary (result of computing $\text{sgn}(\cdot)$, length of the representative vector).

Definition 3.2 (Representative vector). Let $\pi: \mathbb{V} \rightarrow \mathcal{A}$ be the mapping that sends a vector to its direction. A **representative vector** of direction d is any fixed vector $\mathbf{v}_d \in \pi^{-1}(d)$. Choosing representatives is a section $\sigma: \mathcal{A} \rightarrow \mathbb{V}$, $\pi \circ \sigma = \text{id}_{\mathcal{A}}$.

Depending on the problem, different representatives may be used. The table below shows two options: those with integer coordinates and normalized ones (length = 1).

Remark 3.2. Choosing representatives does not change the classes themselves. It is only a technical convenience for constructing tables and examples.

Table 1.2

Canonical representatives

d	representative (integer)	representative (normalized)
\rightarrow	$(1, 0)$	$(1, 0)$
\leftarrow	$(-1, 0)$	$(-1, 0)$
\uparrow	$(0, 1)$	$(0, 1)$
\downarrow	$(0, -1)$	$(0, -1)$
\nearrow	$(1, 1)$	$\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$
\nwarrow	$(-1, 1)$	$\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$
\swarrow	$(-1, -1)$	$\left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$
\searrow	$(1, -1)$	$\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, -\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\right)$

3.0.4 From Equivalence Class to Elementary Function

The key observation for classimetry is that the elementary R -function $F_d(x, y)$ (see §1.1, item 5) is an invariant of the equivalence class:

Theorem 3.1 (Invariance of the elementary function). For any vector $\mathbf{v} = (x, y)$ belonging to the class $d \in \mathcal{A}$, the value $F_d(x, y)$ is positive. For a vector from another class, the sign of F_d can be anything, but the function F_d as an expression does not depend on the choice of representative inside the class.

Proof. For sectoral directions ($\nearrow, \nwarrow, \swarrow, \searrow$) the function F_d has the form $\pm x \wedge^0 \pm y$. Inside the class the signs of $\pm x$ and $\pm y$ are fixed, and $x \wedge^0 y = \min(x, y)$ whenever $x + y \geq 0$. Since x and y have the same sign, $x + y \geq 0$ holds automatically for all vectors of the class. Positivity follows from $x > 0, y > 0$ (or the appropriate sign combinations).

For axial directions the function F_d has the form $\frac{(\pm x)\delta^2}{y^2 + \delta^2}$ (or with y). Inside the class the zero coordinate is identically zero, while the sign of the non-zero coordinate is fixed, guaranteeing positivity. \square

3.0.5 Boundaries between Equivalence Classes

The equivalence classes of one-segment polylines are separated by **boundaries** — the set of vectors for which at least one coordinate is zero (but not both simultaneously, otherwise the vector would be zero).

Definition 3.3 (Boundary vectors). The set of boundary vectors is

$$\partial\mathbb{V} = \{(x, 0) \mid x \neq 0\} \cup \{(0, y) \mid y \neq 0\}.$$

These vectors correspond to the axial directions, with the important nuance that the axial directions themselves are **included** in the classes (they are closed from the side of the sectors). Thus the boundary between sectoral classes runs through the axial directions, which are separate classes.

Remark 3.3. Topological picture: four open sectoral classes (dimension 2) and four closed axial classes (dimension 1, rays). Together they form a partition of \mathbb{V} .

3.0.6 Significance for Classimetry

The notion of an equivalence class of a one-segment polyline serves as the foundation for the whole further theory:

- (i) **Hierarchy.** The classes of one-segment polylines are the atomic level. The classes of n -segment polylines (Chapters 4–5) are constructed as Cartesian products of one-segment classes with additional conditions (e.g., closure);
- (ii) **Self-similarity.** Any fragment of a polyline, regardless of its length, consists of edges each belonging to one of the 8 classes. This allows us to apply the same R -functions recursively;
- (iii) **Discrete-continuous bridge.** A class is a discrete notion (8 symbols). Inside the class there is a continuum of geometric realizations. The R -function F_d gives a continuous numerical characteristic of the position of a vector inside the class;
- (iv) **Transitions.** A change of class during a continuous deformation occurs only when the boundary is crossed — when a vector becomes axial. This is the key property for analyzing the dynamics of shape (Chapter 6).

3.0.7 Examples

Example 3.1 (Inside a class). The vectors $\mathbf{v} = (2, 1)$ and $\mathbf{w} = (100, 0.5)$ both belong to the class \nearrow . Despite the differences in length and angle, their path code is the same, and the elementary R -function $x \wedge^0 y$ is positive for both.

Example 3.2 (On the boundary). The vector $\mathbf{v} = (3, 0)$ belongs to the class (\rightarrow) . From the viewpoint of the neighboring sectoral classes (\nearrow and \searrow) it is a boundary vector. A small perturbation of y from 0 to a positive or negative value changes the code to \nearrow or \searrow , respectively.

Example 3.3 (Crossing the boundary). Consider the family $\mathbf{v}(t) = (1, t)$, $t \in [-1, 1]$. For $t > 0$ the code is (\nearrow); for $t = 0$ the code is (\rightarrow) ; for $t < 0$ the code is (\searrow). The R -function $F_{(\nearrow)}(1, t) = 1 \wedge^0 t$ is positive for $t > 0$ and becomes zero for $t \leq 0$ (by the definition of \wedge^0).

3.0.8 Connection with Bézier Curves and Splines

The control polygon of a Bézier curve (or a B-spline) is a polygonal contour. Consequently, the path code of this polygon becomes a discrete invariant of the curve itself.

- (i) **Quadratic Bézier curves** (3 control points, 2 edges) are completely determined by the code $(d_1, d_2) \in \mathcal{A}^2$. A continuous deformation of the middle control point changes the code only when one of the edges crosses a coordinate axis. This yields a classification of quadratic Bézier curves into 64 types (Chapter 4).
- (ii) **Cubic Bézier curves** (4 points, 3 edges) correspond to $8^3 = 512$ formal codes.
- (iii) **B-splines** with $n+1$ control points have n edges in the control polygon. Their classimetric classification yields 8^n formal codes, which are then reduced by smoothness conditions (e.g., knot multiplicity) and contour closure.

Thus, classimetry is directly applicable to the analysis and monitoring of a wide class of parametric curves given by control polygons: Bézier curves, B-splines. A change of the path code during a deformation of the control points predicts qualitative changes of the curve (appearance of a loop, an inflection point, a change of convexity) long before these changes become visually noticeable.

Summary of Chapter 1

In this chapter we laid down the conceptual and formal foundations of the anisotropic approach to encoding directions in classimetry:

- (i) The **anisotropic alphabet** \mathcal{A} of eight symbols (4 axial, 4 sectoral) partitions the set of non-zero vectors into equivalence classes according to sign patterns.
- (ii) **Elementary direction functions** F_d are positive inside their own class; sectoral directions use classical R -functions (\wedge^0), while axial directions use regularized \tilde{R} -functions (Chapter 3).
- (iii) The **path code** of a polyline is a tuple of directions of its edges. It is a discrete invariant and determines a cell in the parameter space.
- (iv) **Hierarchy and self-similarity** allow us to construct R -functions for polylines of arbitrary length as a conjunction of elementary functions.
- (v) **Application to Bézier curves and splines**: the path code of the control polygon serves as a discrete invariant of Bézier curves (quadratic, cubic, and higher degrees) and B-splines, opening a way to their classification and monitoring.

End of Chapter 1